

**CONDENSATIONS OF ARYL DIAZONIUM SALTS WITH REACTIVE
UNSATURATED COMPOUNDS. PART I. ACTION OF ARYL
DIAZONIUM CHLORIDES WITH CITRACONIC
AND MESACONIC ACIDS**

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Aryl diazonium chlorides containing negative substituents react with citraconic acid and mesaconic acid in the presence of acetone, sodium acetate (buffer) and copper chloride to give α -methyl- β -aryl acrylic acids. The formation of the latter in place of the $\beta\beta$ -isomer supports Koelsch's free radical mechanism for such condensations.

Aryl diazonium chlorides can react with $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compounds under certain conditions (Meerwein, Buchner and Emster, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, 152, 237; Koelsch *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 57; 1944, 66, 412) to give products in which the aryl group and the chlorine atom first add on to the unsaturated linkage, thus

where X=COOR, COOH, CN, -CHO etc., depending upon the orienting influence of the group (R). The change occurs as in (1) if R is an unsaturated group *e. g.*, the vinyl and as in (2) if R is an alkyl group. These studies mostly relate to compounds containing only one activating group (X). Little is known about compounds which contain two such groups *e. g.*

In methyl ester of fumaric acid (I, R''=H; X=CO₂Me) only one aryl addition product can result (Meerwein *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). But in other cases aryl addition may occur at the α and/or β carbon atom according to the influence of the group R'' on the orienting capacity of one of the activating group (X) which would function like the unsaturated group (R) in (1). In the present investigation the action of certain aryl diazonium chlorides has been studied with citraconic and mesaconic acids (I, R''=Me; X=COOH) to ascertain the influence of the methyl group upon the position occupied by the aryl group in the reaction products with the acids.

In case of a reaction going on as in (1), it is found that the elements of hydrogen chloride are usually lost during the course of the reaction. If the group (X) happens

prepared by the isomerisation of citraconic acid by a trace of bromine in chloroform in sunlight (Fittig, *Annalen*, 1877, 188, 73). *p*-Bromobenzaldehyde was obtained by the oxidation of *p*-bromotoluene ("Organic Synthesis", Collective vol., II, p. 442).

Condensation of p-Nitrobenzene diazonium Chloride with Citraconic Acid.—*p*-Nitroaniline (8.9 g.) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (12.5 c.c.), the hydrochloride, precipitated by ice-water (15 c. c.), was diazotised with sodium nitrite (3.5 g.) in water (10 c. c.). The filtered diazonium solution was added to citraconic acid (6.5 g.) in acetone (30 c. c.) containing sodium acetate (11.5 g.), copper chloride (2 g.) dissolved in water (15 c. c.). The mixture was stirred throughout the brisk reaction which lasted for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. A reddish brown solid separated which was filtered off, washed and then extracted with warm saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (10 c. c., thrice). The extract on acidification gave a yellowish white solid (1.5 g.). It was dried, and then triturated in the cold with benzene (5 c. c., thrice) to remove *p*-nitrophenol etc. The benzene-insoluble portion was crystallised from boiling alcohol in rhombic crystals (A), m. p. 208-209°. (Found: N, 6.8; equiv., 202. $C_{10}H_9O_4N$ requires N, 6.76 per cent. Equiv., 207). It decolourised 1% potassium permanganate and bromine water immediately in the cold. The neutral residue failed to give these reactions of unsaturation. The acid (III) of m. p. 168° (*cf.* Wulfung, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1593; Koelsch *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 413) was absent in the mother-liquor left behind after crystallising out the acid (A).

In a separate experiment the gas evolved was first scrubbed through a wash bottle containing water (acidulated with hydrochloric acid to minimise solubility of CO_2) to retain acetone vapours etc, and then through clear saturated baryta water, protected from the outside carbon dioxide. Considerable amount of barium carbonate was obtained. A blank experiment, without citraconic acid, gave only a little opalescence.

*Preparation of α -Methyl-*p*-nitrocinnamic Acid.*—A mixture of *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1.1 g.), anhydrous sodium propionate (0.6 g.) and propionic anhydride (3 c. c.) was heated under reflux at 180° for 8 hours. The mass was slightly cooled and extracted with warm sodium carbonate solution. The extract on acidification gave a solid as rhombic plates from alcohol, m. p. 208° (mixed m. p. with the acid A in the previous experiment, 206-208°). This acid had been obtained by Bisringer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 1235) by the oxidation of α -methyl-*p*-nitrocinnamic aldehyde.

Condensation of p-Bromobenzene diazonium Chloride with Citraconic Acid.—*p*-Bromoaniline (8.6 g.) dissolved in hydrochloric acid (12.5 c. c.) and ice-water (15 c.c.) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (3.5 g.) in water (10 c. c.). The diazotised solution was condensed with a mixture of citraconic acid (6.5 g.), acetone (30 c. c.), sodium acetate (11.5 g.), copper chloride (2 g.), water (15 c. c.) as before. The reaction was brisk and lasted for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The brownish semi-solid mass on extraction with warm aqueous sodium bicarbonate yielded an acid (1.2 g.) which on crystallisation from petroleum ether separated in colourless needles, m. p. 172-73°. (Found: Br, 32.98; equiv., 236. $C_{10}H_7O_2Br$ requires Br, 33.1 per cent. Equiv., 241). It gave tests for unsaturation, whereas the neutral residue did not, showing the absence of stilbene. In a separate experiment the gas phase was found to contain carbon dioxide,

*Preparation of α -Methyl-*p*-bromocinnamic Acid.*—*p*-Bromobenzaldehyde (1.4 g.), anhydrous sodium propionate (0.6 g.) and propionic anhydride (3 c. c.) were refluxed for 8 hours at 170°. The cooled mass was extracted with warm aqueous sodium carbonate. The extract on acidification yielded an acid which crystallised from ether as white needles, m. p. 172-73° (mixed m. p. with the acid in the previous experiment).

Condensation of other Aryl Diazonium chlorides with Citraconic Acid.—Condensations were effected using amine (0.5*M*) and the acid, and sodium acetate (11.5 g.) just as in the first experiment. The melting points and other relevant properties of the corresponding α -methyl- β -aryl-acrylic acids are recorded below as given in the literature for the sake of comparison.

α -Methyl- β -aryl-acrylic acids

Amine (diazotised) and wt.	Nature and time.	Crude mixture.	Properties of pure acids.		Equivalent weight	
			Found.	As given in lit.	Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Nitro- aniline (6.9 g.)	Very brisk; 1½ hrs	Brown, semi-solid	m. p. 198-99° (from petroleum ether) in prisms.	m. p. 196° (from alcohol) in monoclinic prisms.	203	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N : 207
<i>m</i> -Nitro- aniline (6.9 g.)	Do; 1 hr.	Brown, solid	m. p. 196-97°; yellow fine crys- tals from alcohol	m. p. † 197.5° powder. Sol. in alcohol, ether benzene, less in ligroin.	204	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N : 207
α -Naphthyl- amine (7.15 g.)	Slow; 1 hr.	Reddish brown, solid and tar	m. p. 150, needles from benzene.	m. p. † 151°, needles from benzene	208	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ : 212
β -Naphthyl- amine (7.15 g.)	Brisk; 1 hr.	Rose coloured	m. p. 117-22°	Nil	190	Slightly impure

* Ranfaldi, *Rend. R. Accad. Scienze Fis. Mat. Napoli*, 1910, (3), 16, 0.226; *Z. Kr.*, 52, 314.

† Rohde, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1900.

‡ Rousset, *Bul. soc. chim.*, 1897 *iii*, 17, 313.

Nitrobenzene diazonium chlorides (*o*, *m* & *p*) could react even in the presence of 7 g. sodium acetate (p_n ca. 1-3). Higher amounts (22 g.) or the use of borax (14 g.) was found beneficial (p_n ca. 7-9) only in the case of naphthalene diazonium chlorides; in other cases this caused slackening in the evolution of the gas. The β -naphthalene salt reacted more readily than the α -isomer. In every case considerable amounts of neutral tarry matter, consisting presumably of diphenyl derivatives, the parent hydrocarbon, and its halogen derivatives etc., were also present. Also under the above conditions, reactions could not be brought about with diazotised aniline, sulphanilic acid and anthranilic acid.

*Condensation of *p*-Nitrobenzene diazonium Chloride with Mesaconic Acid.*—Diazotised *p*-nitroaniline (6.9) was condensed with mesaconic acid (6.5 g.) in the presence of other

ingredients as in the first experiment. The reaction was not as brisk (3-2½ hours) as in the case of citraconic acid. A brown solid was obtained (1.2 g.) from which after extraction with sodium carbonate, acidification of the extract, trituration with benzene, a solid was obtained which crystallised out from boiling alcohol in prisms, m. p. 208° (mixed m. p. with the acid A).

Work is in progress to utilise condensations of the above type to synthesise cinnamic acid and arylpropionic acids.

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